

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of studying issues related to business bankruptcy under unfavorable macroeconomic conditions stems from the fact that businesses face financial difficulties during crises, recessions, or other negative macroeconomic factors (e.g., pandemics, sanctions, global economic shocks). Supporting businesses during difficult times can help the overall economy recover more quickly. This can be particularly important for small and medium-sized enterprises which comprise a large part of the economy.

Bankruptcy of companies can lead to mass layoffs and worsen the social situation of employees. A temporary moratorium can protect entrepreneurs from unjustified bankruptcy, allowing them to reorganize their businesses and find ways to recover. Introducing a moratorium requires reviewing bankruptcy legislation and practices, which can lead to more flexible and adaptive mechanisms that promote business sustainability.

Thus, the bankruptcy moratorium in economic instability is essential for understanding business support mechanisms and financial sustainability.

The article aims to analyze and understand the implications of bankruptcy moratorium for different participants in economic processes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were publications in peer-reviewed journals in economics, law and management that deal with the topic of bankruptcy, moratorium and their impact on the economy: Regional Research of Russia, European Journal of Law and Economics, Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics, European Business Organization Law Review, SN Business & Economics, India Studies in Business and Economics, Journal of Banking Regulation, European Business Organization Law Review.

Research methods were: case analysis (analysis of specific cases of bankruptcy moratorium in different countries, including successful and unsuccessful examples) and comparative study (comparing bankruptcy moratorium practices in other countries to identify best practices and approaches).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The COVID-19 pandemic had a profound impact on the economy, particularly on business bankruptcy rates worldwide.

As H. P. Marutschke writes, the most dramatic changes can be seen in the performance of medium and small companies and the self-employed who run tiny businesses. The author notes that numerous companies struggle to survive or have gone bankrupt despite extensive financial support policies. Creditors find it difficult to collect their debts such as rent and unpaid invoices for goods supplied, and debtors seek to get rid of their debts, which is not easy as it would require bankruptcy proceedings [1].

S. Zemtsov et al. write that small and medium-sized businesses suffered from the fall in consumer demand in 2020-2021 and, therefore, became objects of anti-crisis support worldwide. According to the authors, business digitalization proved to be an effective way of adaptation, and the policy of state support could be more effective in regions with the most remarkable “digital maturity” [2].

J. I. Shatokhina et al. write that because of COVID-19, countries’ governments direct significant efforts to develop measures to support small and medium-sized businesses. The authors identified the directions of business support measures during the pandemic by the central support subjects: preferential financing in the form of loans and credit lines, grants and targeted subsidies, measures to preserve employment, support for companies – participants in public procurement, and others [3].

S. Muzi et al. show that more productive firms are more likely to survive during the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. They indicate the importance of digitalization and management innovation for smaller organizations [4].

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted the bankruptcy rate of businesses in European countries. The hotel, restaurant and tourism sectors were particularly hard hit – numerous companies in these areas faced a total loss of income, accelerating their bankruptcy.

R. Blazy and N. Stef analyze the content of bankruptcy cases handled by courts operating in three Eastern European countries: Hungary, Poland, and Romania. The authors found that investors’ ability to recover strongly depends on the local rules prevailing after the bankruptcy filing and on the type of procedure involved (reorganization or liquidation) [5].

F. Eckert and H. Mikosch started monthly monitoring company bankruptcies and startup activity in Switzerland in June 2020 [6].

D. Varadzhakova et al. investigate the socioeconomic impact of the pandemic on Bulgaria's tourism industry and review the measures taken to support one of the country's most affected sectors [7].

D. Ionut et al. write that deferring debt payments during the COVID-19 pandemic in Romania was a logical and beneficial step for all stakeholders. The authors believe that a COVID-19 macroeconomic shock could lead to a significant increase in NPLs, negatively impacting the banking sector's ability to lend to the real economy [8].

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted the Chinese economy, which in turn affected business bankruptcy. The services and tourism industry, restaurants, hotels, and entertainment establishments were the most affected.

Z. Zhang examines China's participation in the global cross-border bankruptcy cooperation system. The author concludes that foreign bankruptcy representatives face significant difficulties in satisfying the requirements of contract and reciprocity when seeking relief from China. Local protectionism favoring Chinese state-owned and state-affiliated companies undermines the confidence of foreign bankruptcy representatives in seeking support from Chinese courts [9].

The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the Indian economy. Industries such as tourism, hospitality, retail, transportation, and services were hit the hardest.

K. Manikyamba et al. opine that an effective insolvency law provides an established legal framework through judicial intervention or out of court settlement. According to the authors' data for 2019, India ranked 108th out of 190 countries for insolvency resolution, an improvement from 16th rank in 2017. Insolvency proceedings take 4 to 3 years and cost about 9% of the proceeds from selling the debtor's property. The insolvency index score increased from 6 in 2017 to 8.5 in 2018 [10]. According to R. Sane, this was due to the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code passed in 2016 by the Indian Parliament [11; 12].

D. Tandon and N. Tandon write that the code offers a comprehensive insolvency law and consistent and harmonized provisions for stakeholders affected by the inability to repay debt or business bankruptcy [13].

Ali H. Mohd concludes that Malaysia has adequate laws to meet the restructuring needs of affected companies during the pandemic. Courts are concerned with protecting creditors but are willing to help distressed companies overcome their predicament [14].

A. Goswami believes that Non-performing assets (NPAs) have long been one of the most prominent and frightening problems that have shaken the entire banking industry worldwide. The author tries to clarify the facts related to NPAs that have damaged the reliability, profitability, and productivity of the Indian banking industry from 2019 to 2020. The author has statistically

proved that serious policy measures and minor impacts of the COVID-19 crisis contributed to the decline in NPA from 1999 to 2020 [15].

M. Gruszczyński writes that information about financial problems, bankruptcy, and other types of company termination is crucial for capital owners, management, creditors, investors, and other stakeholders [16].

S. Shafiai et al. write that banks, by providing their customers with such financial assistance as a moratorium, may jeopardize their financial position because they will have to offer new credit to existing borrowers [17].

Thus, the scientific problem in the present research is the need for a deep analysis and understanding of the consequences of a moratorium on bankruptcy for various participants in economic processes.

It is necessary to investigate how effective the bankruptcy moratorium is in actual conditions. The question is whether it helps save businesses and jobs or prolongs the liquidation process of insolvent companies.

Introducing a moratorium may affect the interests of different groups: creditors, shareholders, employees, and the state. The research problem is balancing business protection and creditors' rights and minimizing the adverse effects on all parties.

It is essential to investigate how a temporary bankruptcy moratorium affects the long-term sustainability of the economy, for example, whether it can lead to the accumulation of bad debts and deterioration of companies' financial condition in the future.

Examining international experience with bankruptcy moratoriums in different countries reveals best practices and approaches that can be adapted to country-specific conditions.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

COVID-19's negative impact on the world economy and the economies of individual countries in particular became, in fact, one of the severest tests of recent times. During the period under review, numerous areas of business worldwide were on the verge of bankruptcy.

Spain

By April 6, the number of infected people in Spain reached almost 150,000. The country was also prohibited from considering creditors' applications for forced liquidation of debtors. Companies were exempted from the obligation to file for bankruptcy, which also aimed to reduce the financial burden on businesses.

Restrictions in Spain were lifted two months after the emergency ended, and bankruptcy applications from debtors were prioritized.

France

Due to the rapid spread of the disease, France was placed under a sanitary emergency regime from March 24 to May 24. The bankruptcy law was amended so that the existence of signs of bankruptcy before August 24 (unless the emergency regime was extended) was determined as of March 12. If a company was not in a “suspension of payments” status at that time, it could choose not to file for bankruptcy if its financial situation deteriorated and creditors were unable to initiate the process.

Moreover, companies could take advantage of any bankruptcy procedures that might not have been available to them under normal circumstances. In addition to external administration or liquidation, procedures to restore the company’s solvency were available (appointment of a special representative, initiation of a financial recovery procedure (*sauvegarde*), and conciliation procedures). At the end of the specified period, companies in “suspension of payments” state were to file for bankruptcy within 45 days.

Germany

In Germany, where the number of COVID-19 victims exceeded 100,000, affected companies were expected to be exempted from the obligation to file for their bankruptcy until September 30; this rule was extended until March 31, 2021. However, it did not apply if the insolvency arose earlier or was not caused by the pandemic and there was no chance of the company repaying its debts. Creditors could file for counterparties’ bankruptcy only if the latter was already insolvent on March 1.

However, additional safeguards were introduced to protect against subsequent payment challenges and actions taken to support or restore business operations or to restructure.

UK

A bill to amend the current insolvency law in the UK was drafted and approved. It proposed suspending debtors’ obligation to initiate bankruptcy proceedings for a specified period, with the changes applying retrospectively from March 1; this aimed to support debtors in the face of the economic instability caused by the pandemic.

US

In light of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Small Business Reorganization Act of 2019 (SBRA) was amended in the US. Under the new Article V of Title 11 of the U.S. Bankruptcy Code, the amount of debt at which small businesses can file for bankruptcy was increased by one year, from 2.7 million to 7.5 million USD. This change was to help debtors retain more control over their businesses, simplify the reorganization approval process, and reduce the time and cost of bankruptcy.

In addition, consumers experiencing financial hardship due to the pandemic were able to make changes to their previously approved reorganization plan, including extending their payments for up to 7 years. These measures were intended to ease the financial burden on households and small businesses in the current economic climate.

Asia-Pacific (APAC) region

Some countries in the APAC region also took measures to prevent mass bankruptcies in the face of a pandemic. For example, in India, the minimum amount of debt to initiate business bankruptcy was increased 100 times to 10 million rupees (approximately 130,000 USD). This decision aimed to protect small and medium-sized enterprises from financial difficulties caused by the crisis.

In Singapore, the debt required to file for bankruptcy was increased to the equivalent of 70,000 USD. This also created a broader 'filter' to protect financially distressed businesses from immediate bankruptcy.

In Australia, the lower threshold for filing for bankruptcy was increased tenfold to 20,000 AUD, and this change was effective for 6 months. In addition, the time limits for responding to creditor claims in bankruptcy cases and the period of interim protection from debt collection were increased from 21 days to 6 months. During this period, bankruptcy could not be initiated against the debtor, giving businesses additional time to stabilize their financial situation.

Russia

Russia imposed a bankruptcy moratorium on April 1 to protect companies from the financial impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which was very important to support the economy. On April 3, the Russian government applied a 6-month bankruptcy moratorium. The moratorium applied to legal entities and individual entrepreneurs operating in the sectors most affected by the crisis, such as catering, education, sports, transportation, and hospitality. Protective measures included absence of financial penalties for the duration of the moratorium and suspension of compulsory property collection.

Similar measures were observed in other countries affected by the coronavirus. This indicates a global trend towards economic support.

Russia's bankruptcy moratorium is in line with international trends, giving existing companies time to cope with the economic consequences of the pandemic. The measure is designed to help businesses mitigate immediate financial difficulties, allowing them to focus on recovery rather than facing insolvency.

One notable feature of the moratorium is the introduction of mechanisms such as pre-trial agreements with creditors. This can facilitate constructive negotiations and allow financially viable companies to reach debt repayment agreements, thereby preserving their operations.

Nevertheless, there are serious concerns about the potential abuse of the moratorium. Unscrupulous market participants could use these measures as a defense to delay necessary payments, benefiting from temporary restrictions on creditors' collection actions. This could lead to a broader default crisis, putting financial pressure on creditors and potentially leading them into bankruptcy.

The moratorium also includes provisions on transaction validity – any transaction exceeding 1% of a company's assets during the moratorium period can be invalidated. This creates additional difficulties for affected companies, limiting their ability to engage with potential business partners and effectively deal with the crisis. However, a recent amendment signed by the President on April 24, removing the invalidity provision, may alleviate some of these difficulties by giving companies greater flexibility in managing their affairs.

Ultimately, while the moratorium serves as a temporary relief measure, its effectiveness in supporting the economy depends on the broader context. If the measures implemented by the authorities and the strategies employed by businesses prove insufficient to address economic problems in the coming months, a moratorium may delay the inevitable bankruptcies rather than prevent them. Ongoing evaluation and adjustments to support mechanisms will be critical to determine whether a moratorium can contribute to long-term stability and recovery.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Various companies may face financial difficulties during economic crises, recessions, or other negative macroeconomic factors such as high inflation, falling demand, or global economic turmoil.

A bankruptcy moratorium can help save jobs and prevent mass bankruptcies, which can help the economy recover more quickly.

In a crisis, governments may impose bankruptcy moratoria as part of anti-crisis measures to support businesses and prevent social consequences [18].

On the other hand, a prolonged moratorium may lead to accumulation of debts and deterioration of the financial condition of companies, which may create even more significant problems in the future [19].

It is necessary to consider the legal aspects of imposing a moratorium, as well as its impact on creditors and the financial system as a whole [20].

Studying the experience of other countries that introduced moratoria on bankruptcy during crisis periods can provide valuable lessons and recommendations [21].

Thus, the topic has numerous aspects for discussion and analysis, and may be of interest to both researchers and practitioners in economics and law.

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